

Thermal Decomposition Kinetics of Thorium(IV) and Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes[#]

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Thermal decomposition kinetics studies of thermal reactions are useful in studying parameters like free energy change (ΔG^*), enthalpy change (ΔH^*), activation energy (E^*) and ultimately the entropy change (ΔS^*) and pre-exponential factor (A) or frequency factor (Z). This concept was first proposed somewhere in 1928. Since then so many methods and equations have been put forward for studying thermal decomposition kinetics of the reaction. Present report discusses some aspects of non-isothermal kinetic studies of some thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes with various pyrazolones, amine *N*-oxides and aromatic Schiff bases.

Thermal decomposition studies of a material are useful in predicting the thermal stability of that material as chemical changes in the material can be studied with the help of TGA, DTG and DTA studies of the material. That is why the thermal properties are among the important properties of any substance. Kinetic studies of thermal decomposition reactions may become useful in calculating the important parameters like activation energy (E^*), free energy change (ΔG^*), enthalpy change (ΔH^*), entropy change (ΔS^*) and pre-exponential factor (A) for thermal reactions of a substance, which directly govern the factors of thermal stability of any substance.

Thermal decomposition kinetics was proposed by Flynn¹. However, as Flynn pointed out, the concept had already been set forth many years before, as for example, in 1928 Akahira proposed a new concept of equivalent temperature at which the chemical reaction proceeds non-isothermally². In 1958, Freeman and Carroll published their method for kinetic analysis of thermoanalytical data³. Since then various methods for kinetic analysis have been proposed⁴. This tendency stimulated new development of thermal decomposition kinetics rather non-isothermal kinetics. Some methods for kinetic analysis can be derived without the non-isothermal kinetics, but widely applicable methods are derived on the basis of non-isothermal concept or non-isothermal kinetics as analysis of thermoanalytical curves of some reaction according to isothermal concept resulted in the false and unreal kinetic parameters. Therefore, various types of isothermal kinetic equations were extended to the non-isothermal relations. Some methods that have been put forward for estimation of the kinetic parameters are the methods of Coats-Redfern⁵, Horowitz-Metzger⁶, Dharwadkar-Karkhanawala⁷, Zsako Doyle⁸ and Fuoss *et al.*⁹ (equations 1 to 5).

$$F - C - \frac{(E^*/2.30R)\Delta T^{-1}}{\Delta \log W_r} = -b + \frac{\Delta \log dw/dt}{\Delta \log W_r} \quad (1)$$

$$H - M \log \log \frac{W_c}{W_r} = \frac{E^* \theta}{2-3RT_s^2} - \log 2.3 \quad (2)$$

$$C-R \log \left\{ \frac{1-(1-\alpha)^{1-b}}{T^2(1-b)} \right\} = \log \left\{ \frac{ZR}{aE^*} \frac{(1-2RT)}{E^*} - \frac{E^*}{2-3RT} \right\} \quad (3)$$

for $b \neq 1$

$$\log \left\{ \frac{-\log(1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right\} = \log \left\{ \frac{ZR}{aE^*} \frac{(1-2RT)}{E^*} - \frac{E^*}{2-3RT} \right\} \quad (3)$$

for $b = 1$

$$\text{Fuoss / K-D} \quad E = - \left[\frac{RT_i^2}{W_i} \right] \left[\frac{dW}{dT} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Zsako} \quad \log \frac{ZE}{Rq} = \log g(a) - \log p(x) = B \quad (5)$$

where E is the activation energy, Z the collision frequency, b the order of reaction; $W_r = W_c - W$ (W_c = weight-loss at completion of reaction and W = total weight-loss upto time t); R is the gas constant, T the absolute temperature, T_s the reference temperature such that at $T_s = \frac{|W|}{W_o} = \frac{1}{E}$; $\theta = T - T_s$;

α is the conversion degree, a or q the heating rate, T_i the temperature of inflexion, W_i the weight at T_i and $(dW/dT)_i$ is slope at the point of inflexion. An apparent activation entropy can be calculated using equation (8),

$$\Delta S^* = 2.303 R \log \frac{Zh}{kT} \quad (6)$$

So far workers have applied these methods, depending upon their needs and conditions for kinetic analysis of thermal decomposition reactions of the solid substance¹⁰⁻¹². Kinetics of thermal decomposition reactions of many coordination compounds of transition metals have also been reported. The thermal stability of Schiff base synthesised from 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and sulphamethoxy-pyridazine; sulphamethazole or sulphafurazole and their Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} chelates was investigated and activation energy values were also predicted¹³. Murthy and Rao¹⁴ investigated that E_{act} values for $ML_2C_2O_4$ ($L = 1,3$ -diaminopropan-2-ol) are 25.65, 17.32, 25.22 and 20.95 kcal

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mol⁻¹ for M = Co, Ni, Zn and Cd respectively, using Dharwadkar-Karkhanawala method⁷. For the reactions in which the complex loses one molecule of the ligand, the overall order is unity. Kinetics of thermal decomposition of M₂LCl_n (M = Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺; n = 4, and M = Fe³⁺; n = 6 when L = bis((antipyril)methyl)piperazine) and MZnLCl_n (M = Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, n = 4, and M = Fe²⁺; n = 5) the compounds were studied by C-R⁵ and Zsako⁸ integral methods¹⁵. The kinetic parameters were calculated for dehydrated bis(2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinato)cobalt(II) and -nickel(II) complexes and it was found that desoluation decomposition process of these complexes follows first order kinetics¹⁶. *cis*-[Pt(PEt₃)₂ RCl] (R = Pr, Bu) complexes undergo isomerization and thermal decomposition in Me₂CHOH depending upon the experimental conditions (addition of LiCl, PEt₃). Kinetics of β-hydrogen elimination from this complex were suggested¹⁷. Reaction orders and *E*_{act} were determined as 0.56, 0.59 and 0.60 and 11.03 kcal mol⁻¹; 15.70 and 18.51 kcal mol⁻¹ for non-isothermal decomposition of Co^{II} complexes of 5-phenylazosalicylaldehyde¹⁸. Non-isothermal kinetic studies of the decomposition of Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ru^{III}, Pt^{IV}, VO^{IV}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes with various Schiff base ligands, N-donor ligands as antipyrine, pyrimidines and substituted pyrimidines, salicylidene aminofluorene pyridines, picolines including *N*-oxide ligands, substituted indole, fluorenone thiosemicarbazone, substituted oxamates including various coordination polymers have been reported in literature¹⁹⁻³³.

Thermal properties (TGA, DTA and DTG) of actinides coordination compounds specially thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) metal complexes have also been a part of attention of many workers³⁹⁻⁵², but less work has been done so far on the non-isothermal kinetic analysis Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II} coordination compounds³⁴⁻³⁸. Thermal behaviour of uranyl(VI) complexes with thiourea was examined and Δ*H* values for decomposition reactions were evaluated³⁴. The thermal decomposition of some mixed uranyl Schiff base and DMSO, ETOH or Ph₃PO complexes were studied and *E*_{act} and Δ*H* of dissociation reactions were calculated³⁵. The thermal decomposition of Th^{IV} chelates of 1-(2-fluorenylazo)-2-naphthol and *o*-carboxyphenylazo-2-naphthol has been studied by TGA, the order of reaction and energy and entropy of activation are given³⁷ and the relative stability of these chelates is also discussed. Though thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes of various pyrazolone and substituted pyrazolones³⁹⁻⁴¹, *N*-oxides⁴²⁻⁴⁸, sulphoxides⁴⁹⁻⁵² and that of the Schiff bases⁵³⁻⁵⁸ have been studied, but less attention has been paid for non-isothermal kinetic analysis of thorium(IV) and uranyl(VI) complexes.

This report presents the summarised results of the non-isothermal kinetic analysis done on different thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes in our laboratory.

Results and Discussion

Three different methods that were used to evaluate the kinetic parameters from the TGA traces of thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes are presented below.

*Freeman-Carroll method*³ :

Freeman and Carroll gave an idea about the evaluation of kinetic parameters using the equation,

$$-\int \frac{dx}{dt} = \int A \exp. \left\{ -E^*/RT \right\} x^b \quad (7)$$

for the general reaction,

$$aA = bB + cC \quad (8)$$

where the symbols have their usual meanings. They solved this equation and found out the results for studying the kinetic parameters of thermal decomposition reactions which is given in equation (1), from which one may conclude that on plotting

$$\frac{\Delta \log (dw/dt)}{\Delta \log W_r} \text{ vs } \frac{(\Delta T^{-1})}{\Delta \log W_r} \quad (9)$$

one may be able to find out *b* as intercept and $-E^*/2.303R$ as the slope from where *E*^{*} can be computed.

*Coats-Redfern method*⁵:

For the similar types of reactions, Coats-Redfern also derived some relation relating α (conversion degree) and all other parameters. This relation is given in equation (3). One may apply these equations to the thermal decomposition data and may plot

$$\log \left\{ \frac{-\log (1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right\} \text{ vs } \frac{1}{T} \text{ (for } n = 1) \quad (10)$$

If these plots are straight-line this confirms that the reactions may have order unity. *E*^{*} can be obtained from the slopes of curves and *Z* from the intercepts; Δ*S*^{*} can be computed using equation (6).

*Horowitz-Metzger method*⁶ :

The method of Horowitz-Metzger is illustrative of the approximation methods. They derived the relation for such reactions given in equation (2), which may be written as

$$\log \left\{ \log \frac{W_c}{W_r} \right\} = \frac{E^* \theta}{2.3 RT_s^2} - \log 2.3 \quad (11)$$

E^{*} for the reactions can be calculated from the slopes of the plots of

$$\log \left\{ \log \frac{W_c}{W_r} \right\} \text{ vs } \theta \quad (12)$$

and *Z* can be calculated using the equation,

$$\frac{E^*}{RT_s^2} = \frac{Z}{q \exp. \{-E^*/RT_s\}} \quad (13)$$

These methods have been applied to different complexes of thorium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) and it was inferred that all the thermal decomposition reactions have the order unity.

Thorium(IV) nitrates complexes of 3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (Mep), 4-vinylpyridine-*N*-oxide (4-VinPyO), 3-methyl-4-nitroso-5-pyrazolone (MNP) and 4-[*N*-(3,4,5-trimethoxybenzalidene)amino]antipyrine (TMBAAP) were prepared by the reported methods⁵⁹⁻⁶¹. These complexes were assigned the general composition according to the physicochemical studies as [Th(MeP)₂(NO₃)₄], [Th(4-VinPyO)₂(NO₃)₄], [Th(MNP)₂(NO₃)₄] and Th(TMBAAP)₂(NO₃)₄. The decomposition data for these complexes is presented in Table 1. All of these complexes show three stages of decomposition with DTG peak temperature *ca* 225–250° for first stage of decomposition except Th(NO₃)₄(TMBAAP)₂ which shows two stages of decomposition with DTG peak temperature at 303° for the first

stage of decomposition. TGA and DTG plots for [Th(MeP)₂(NO₃)₄] (Fig.1) and [Th(MNP)₂(NO₃)₄] were drawn. On the application of the above mentioned methods on the TGA traces of these complexes, *E*^{*}, *Z* and ΔS^* values were obtained⁶¹⁻⁶⁴ for the thermal decomposition reactions (Table 2). *E*^{*} values are sufficiently high while ΔS^* have negative values. These values are comparable with other observations^{32,33,65}. These complexes show similar type of thermal behaviour as is shown by *E*^{*} and *Z* values for the reactions.

TABLE 1—THERMAL DECOMPOSITION DATA FOR THORIUM(IV) COMPLEXES

Compd.	Stage of decomposition	Reaction	Peak temp. in DTG °C	Temp. range in DTG °C
Th(MeP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	First	Th(MeP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄ → Th(MeP)(NO ₃) ₄	225	175–250
	Second	Th(MeP)(NO ₃) ₄ → Th(NO ₃) ₄	345	300–360
	Third	Th(NO ₃) ₄ → ThO ₂	425	400–450
Th(MNP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	First	Th(MNP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄ → Th(MNP)(NO ₃) ₄	225	180–280
	Second	Th(MNP)(NO ₃) ₄ → Th(NO ₃) ₄	335	290–390
	Third	Th(NO ₃) ₄ → ThO ₂	600	560–640
Th(4-VinPyO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	First	Th(4-VinPyO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄ → Th(NO ₃) ₄	250	245–255
	Second	Th(NO ₃) ₄ → ThO ₂	550	540–560
Th(NO ₃) ₄ .2TMBAAP	First	Th(NO ₃) ₄ .2TMBAAP → Th(NO ₃) ₄	303	253–353
	Second	Th(NO ₃) ₄ → ThO ₂	483	443–533

Fig. 1. [Th(MeP)₂(NO₃)₄].

TABLE 2—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR Th^{IV} COMPLEXES ON THE BASIS OF FREEMAN-CARROLL (FC), COATS-REDFERN (CR) AND HOROWITZ-METZGER (HM) METHODS

Compd.	Decomposition stage	Eqn.	<i>E</i> [*] kJmol ⁻¹	<i>Z</i> × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	ΔS^* JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Th(MeP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	First	FC	51.15	—	—
		CR	52.30	2.50	-165.28
		HM	50.41	2.41	-165.28
	Second	FC	32.35	—	—
		CR	35.37	1.10	-173.59
		HM	34.73	1.06	-173.90
	Third	FC	132.35	—	—
		CR	131.15	3.16	-165.83
		HM	135.11	3.25	-165.60
Th(MNP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄	First	FC	16.56	—	—
		CR	11.62	2.66	-157.8
		HM	18.40	3.65	-155.2
	Second	FC	16.56	—	—
		CR	18.82	2.34	-162.22
		HM	17.25	3.77	-158.25
	Third	FC	35.37	—	—

Table-2 (Contd.)

Th(4-VinPyO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄ First	CR	32.53	5.13	-160.5
	HM	34.73	1.09	-173.4
	FC	45.15	-	-
	CR	50.30	2.2	-162.38
	HM	50.14	2.3	-162.82
	Second	FC	127.21	-
Th(TMBAAP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄ First	CR	129.15	3.0	-165.38
	HM	130.15	2.9	-164.28
	FC	24.40	-	-
	CR	24.20	3.1	-148.15
	HM	24.64	3.2	-148.35
	Second	FC	41.90	-
	CR	42.74	2.2	-159.05
	HM	42.43	2.1	-158.79

Fig. 2. [UO₂(MHBAEB)₂(CH₃COO)₂].

Non-isothermal kinetics of ten different dioxouranium(VI) nitrates and acetates complexes with MeP, MPP, MNP, 4-VinPyO, TMBAAP and MHBAEB have been studied. These complexes were prepared by the reported methods^{60,61,66-69}. The complexes have been assigned the general composition [UO₂L₂(NO₃)₂] (L = MeP, MPP, MNP, 4-VinPyO, TMBAAP and MHBAEB) and [UO₂L₂(CH₃-COO)₂] (L = MeP, MPP, MNP and MHBAEB)^{60,61,66,67}. Decomposition data for these complexes is presented in Table 3. All the complexes show similar behaviour in their thermal decomposition (Figs. 2- 4). All the complexes show three stages of decomposition with DTG peaks at 225–250° (for first stage of decomposition), 300–350° (for second

TABLE 3—THERMAL DECOMPOSITION DATA FOR DIOXOURANIUM(VI) COMPLEXES

Compd.	Stage of decomposition	Reaction	Peak temp. in DTG °C	Temp. range in DTG °C
UO ₂ (MeP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	First	UO ₂ (MeP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (MeP) _{1.5} (NO ₃) ₂	180	140–200
	Second	UO ₂ (MeP) _{1.5} (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (MeP)(NO ₃) ₂	285	240–320
	Third	UO ₂ (MeP)(NO ₃) ₂ → [UO ₃] → U ₃ O ₈	545	500–570
UO ₂ (MPP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	First	UO ₂ (MPP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (MPP) _{1.5} (NO ₃) ₂	215	170–270
	Second	UO ₂ (MPP) _{1.5} (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (MPP) _{0.5} (NO ₃) ₂	415	350–510
	Third	UO ₂ (MPP) _{0.5} (NO ₃) ₂ → [UO ₃] → U ₃ O ₈	600	560–700
UO ₂ (MNP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	First	UO ₂ (MNP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (MNP)(NO ₃) ₂	245	220–270
	Second	UO ₂ (MNP)(NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (MNP) _{0.3} (NO ₃) ₂	500	460–530
	Third	UO ₂ (MNP) _{0.3} (NO ₃) ₂ → [UO ₃] → U ₃ O ₈	645	610–670
UO ₂ (4-VinPyO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	First	UO ₂ (4-VinPyO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (4-VinPyO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	227	215–240
	Second	UO ₂ (4-VinPyO)(NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	330	320–340
	Third	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ → [UO ₃] → U ₃ O ₈	625	600–645
UO ₂ (TMBAAP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	First	UO ₂ (TMBAAP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (TMBAAP)(NO ₃) ₂	213	173–253
	Second	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ (TMBAAP) → UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	283	263–323
	Third	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ → [UO ₃] → U ₃ O ₈	483	453–523
UO ₂ (MHBAEB) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	First	UO ₂ (MHBAEB) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (MHBAEB) _{1.2} (NO ₃) ₂	120	100–160
	Second	UO ₂ (MHBAEB) _{1.2} (NO ₃) ₂ → UO ₂ (MHBAEB) _{0.4} (NO ₃) ₂	300	250–320
	Third	UO ₂ (MHBAEB) _{0.4} (NO ₃) ₂ → [UO ₃] → U ₃ O ₈	505	470–560

				Table-3 (Contd.)	
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MeP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	First	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MeP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow \text{UO}_2(\text{MeP})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	265	210-280	
	Second	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MeP})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow \text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2$	305	290-340	
	Third	$\text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow [\text{UO}_3] \rightarrow \text{U}_3\text{O}_8$	705	690-760	
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MPP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	First	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MPP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow \text{UO}_2(\text{MPP})_{0.8}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	250	225-275	
	Second	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MPP})_{0.8}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow \text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	410	380-450	
	Third	$\text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow [\text{UO}_3] \rightarrow \text{U}_3\text{O}_8$	685	650-710	
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MNP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	First	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MNP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow \text{UO}_2(\text{MNP})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	190	160-220	
	Second	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MNP})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow \text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	345	280-390	
	Third	$\text{UO}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow [\text{UO}_3] \rightarrow \text{U}_3\text{O}_8$	730	720-760	
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	First	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow \text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})_{1.7}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	110	80-160	
	Second	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})_{1.7}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow \text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	280	260-300	
	Third	$\text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \rightarrow [\text{UO}_3] \rightarrow \text{U}_3\text{O}_8$	440	390-510	

stage of decomposition) and 600-650°(for third stage of decomposition). On the application of these three methods on the TGA traces of these complexes, E^* and ΔS^* values were obtained^{61-64, 68-70} (Table 4). E^* values for these complexes are sufficiently high and positive while ΔS^* values are negative. These values are comparable with the other observations^{32,33,65}. These complexes show similar type of thermal behaviour as it is shown by E^* and Z values of these reactions.

TABLE 4-KINETIC PARAMETERS OF DIOXOURANIUM(VI) COMPLEXES ON THE BASIS OF FREEMAN-CARROLL (FC), COATS-REDFERN (CR) AND HOROWITZ-METZGER (HM) METHODS

Compd.	Decom- position stage	Eqn.	E^* kJ mol ⁻¹	Z s ⁻¹ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	S^*
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MeP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	First	FC	19.2	-	-
		CR	18.7	1.09×10^4	-171.09
		HM	19.6	1.142×10^4	-170.70
	Second	FC	45.88	-	-
		CR	46.55	1.78×10^4	-168.74
		HM	48.55	1.89×10^4	-168.25
	Third	FC	85.16	-	-
		CR	83.26	1.47×10^4	-173.29
		HM	85.62	1.51×10^4	-173.29
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MPP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	First	FC	15.0	-	-
		CR	12.9	6.30×10^5	-138.0
		HM	12.4	6.22×10^5	-138.1
	Second	FC	11.4	-	-
		CR	11.5	2.91×10^5	-147.3
		HM	14.4	3.63×10^5	-145.4
	Third	FC	38.4	-	-
		CR	39.1	6.14×10^5	-143.0
		HM	40.3	6.32×10^5	-142.8
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MNP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	First	FC	22.56	-	-
		CR	20.94	1.01×10^5	-147.1
		HM	24.22	1.18×10^5	-140.7
	Second	FC	17.53	-	-
		CR	14.07	6.22×10^4	-157.4
		HM	19.59	8.45×10^4	-154.8
	Third	FC	26.53	-	-
		CR	24.63	7.21×10^4	-158.3
		HM	29.55	3.45×10^4	-164.4

				Table-4 (Contd.)		
$\text{UO}_2(4\text{-VinPyO})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	First	FC	18.9	-	-	
		CR	18.7	1.1×10^4	-171.09	
		HM	19.2	1.14×10^4	-170.07	
	Second	FC	48.82	-	-	
		CR	45.81	1.67×10^4	-168.35	
		HM	46.55	1.78×10^4	-168.73	
	Third	FC	83.26	-	-	
		CR	85.61	1.48×10^4	-173.15	
		HM	85.26	1.50×10^4	-173.19	
$\text{UO}_2(\text{TMBAAP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	First	FC	25.23	-	-	
		CR	26.74	6.9×10^4	-149.47	
		HM	25.40	6.6×10^4	-149.84	
	Second	FC	38.50	-	-	
		CR	38.60	5.3×10^4	-154.32	
		HM	39.25	5.5×10^4	-154.01	
	Third	FC	58.98	-	-	
		CR	59.49	3.01×10^4	-163.20	
		HM	59.98	3.03×10^4	-163.20	
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	First	FC	14.92	-	-	
		CR	12.02	8.6×10^5	-133.5	
		HM	12.15	9.6×10^5	-132.6	
	Second	FC	69.33	-	-	
		CR	71.32	3.20×10^4	-164.0	
		HM	67.98	2.49×10^4	-166.1	
	Third	FC	51.53	-	-	
		CR	47.38	2.5×10^4	-168.6	
		HM	53.78	1.05×10^4	-175.9	
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MeP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	First	FC	30.50	-	-	
		CR	30.85	5.2×10^4	-153.63	
		HM	31.58	5.3×10^4	-153.47	
	Second	FC	30.85	-	-	
		CR	31.40	4.0×10^4	-156.98	
		HM	31.84	4.06×10^4	-156.85	
	Third	FC	90.90	-	-	
		CR	91.10	2.17×10^4	-169.03	
		HM	90.29	2.15×10^4	-169.11	
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MPP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	First	FC	41.3	-	-	
		CR	39.7	1.72×10^4	-168.5	
		HM	41.3	1.8×10^4	-168.1	
	Second	FC	33.4	-	-	
		CR	34.1	8.79×10^5	-138.0	
		HM	34.4	8.81×10^5	-137.9	
	Third	FC	41.7	-	-	
		CR	43.7	5.69×10^4	-144.4	
		HM	45.6	5.94×10^4	-144.1	

Table-4 (Contd.)

$\text{UO}_2(\text{MNP})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	First	FC	26.90	-	-
		CR	27.20	8.90×10^4	-146.39
		HM	27.79	9.09×10^4	-146.22
	Second	FC	60.70	-	-
		CR	61.50	6.21×10^4	-154.35
		HM	61.75	6.10×10^4	-154.50
	Third	FC	184.40	-	-
		CR	185.50	4.06×10^4	-164.11
		HM	185.97	4.07×10^4	-164.09
$\text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	First	FC	11.49	-	-
		CR	12.14	9.3×10^5	-132.7
		HM	10.14	8.28×10^5	-133.6
	Second	FC	25.43	-	-
		CR	29.33	8.98×10^5	-136.1
		HM	22.30	8.57×10^5	-136.5
	Third	FC	93.65	-	-
		CR	92.56	3.62×10^4	-164.8
		HM	97.16	2.26×10^4	-168.8

Horowitz-Metzger method gives reasonably good results but it is less accurate mathematically than integral methods. Coats-Redfern method seems to be more accurate but it is a considerable time-consuming method.

Fig. 3. $[\text{UO}_2(\text{MHBAEB})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

Fig. 4. $[\text{UO}_2(\text{MeP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by reported methods^{59-61,66,67}. TGA were recorded on a Santon Red-Craft TG-750 thermobalance at heating rate $10^\circ/\text{min}$ and these TGA curves were used to draw the rate of loss of mass versus temperature (DTG) curves for these complexes.

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